

UNVEILING MATHEMATICS PROFICIENCY CHALLENGES: A COMPREHENSIVE NEEDS ASSESSMENT AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Filipino students have significantly lagged in mathematics education, with over half of this demographic exhibiting inadequate mathematical skills compared to their counterparts in other regions globally. This study focuses on the mathematics performance of Junior High School students in Labasan National High School. Proficiency in mathematical skills and knowledge are essential as they serve as the foundation for everyday life, career advancement, and advancements in science and technology. Mathematics entails more than just logical reasoning; it involves imagination, requiring students to possess creative thinking abilities to delve into mathematical problems. This study conducted a comprehensive needs assessment in the mathematics performance of Junior High School in Labasan National High School. This study employs descriptive research methodology to assess the performance levels in Mathematics of the respondents. Data gathered from 238 students belonging to Grade 7 to Grade 10 undergoes sorting, tabulation, and interpretation, revealing significant gaps in mathematical concepts. The study's findings led to the introduction of an extension program named MathPULSE: Powering Understanding through Learning Support and Education aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 4 (Quality Education), and SDG 5 (Gender Equality). Developed through collaborative efforts between the College of Teacher Education and the Mathematics Club of Mindoro State University – Bongabong Campus, MathPULSE aims to elevate students' proficiency in mathematics. The findings revealed consistent challenges persist among Junior High School students at Labasan National High School regarding mathematics performance, as evidenced by significant score disparities. It also revealed that most students, irrespective of grade level, face difficulties in grasping fundamental mathematical concepts, resulting in consistently low

mean scores across grade levels and highlighting a widespread issue with mathematical performance among students.

Keywords: *Needs Assessment, Mathematics Performance, Sustainable Development Goals, Labasan National High School*

INTRODUCTION

In the landscape of education, mathematics proficiency stands as a critical cornerstone, providing students with essential skills for academic success and future endeavors. Filipino students were among the lowest performing groups of students among all the participating countries in the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). Based on the OECD, PISA (2023), very few students in the Philippines achieved top scores in mathematics.

Labasan National High School, situated in Barangay Labasan, Bongabong, Oriental Mindoro, is renowned as one of the premier educational institutions in the area, esteemed for its dedication to providing top-tier education. Serving as a symbol of academic distinction within the community, Labasan National High School maintains its prestigious reputation through ongoing efforts to innovate and excel in education, ensuring that students receive the highest caliber of learning experiences. Despite the school's academic prowess, many students continue to encounter difficulties with mathematics, struggling to grasp and apply fundamental concepts. Recognizing this challenge, there arises a pressing need for a comprehensive Needs Assessment Study to assess the mathematics performance of Junior High School students at Labasan National High School.

Mathematics plays a pivotal role in education, serving as the cornerstone upon which many other disciplines are built. It equips students with indispensable problem-solving skills, fosters logical reasoning abilities, and nurtures critical thinking capabilities. A robust understanding of mathematics not only facilitates academic success but also lays the groundwork for lifelong learning and personal development. Mathematics provides a framework for understanding complex phenomena and solving real-world problems. Whether calculating probabilities, analyzing data sets, or designing algorithms, mathematical principles underpin many facets of modern society. Therefore, a solid foundation in mathematics empowers individuals to navigate and thrive in an increasingly data-driven and technologically advanced world.

According to Chand, S., et al (2021) students held negative views towards mathematics. The study identified an inadequate secondary school mathematics curriculum as a significant factor contributing to poor academic performance in the subject. It was observed that numerous primary school teachers lacked the necessary skills and proficiency to effectively teach mathematics at their level, which significantly

impacted student engagement and subsequently led to low academic achievement in both upper and lower secondary levels. From the primary levels onward, having a solid foundation in mathematics greatly influences students' ability to tackle challenging subjects in subsequent grade levels. Addressing students' negative views towards mathematics is crucial. Mathematics is not merely a subject to be studied; it is a fundamental tool for understanding the world and shaping the future. By nurturing a strong foundation in mathematics, educators empower students to unlock their full potential, cultivate critical skills, and embark on a journey of lifelong learning and success.

Moreover, proficiency in mathematics opens doors to diverse career opportunities across various fields. From engineering and finance to medicine and computer science, mathematical skills are highly sought after and valued by employers. Beyond specific professions, the analytical mindset cultivated through mathematics education enables individuals to adapt to evolving challenges and pursue their passions with confidence.

Cabuquin, J.C., et al. (2023) revealed a strong and statistically significant correlation between students' proficiency in mathematics and their overall academic success. This suggests that high school students who excel in mathematics also demonstrate higher performance levels across their academic subjects. Fostering proficiency in mathematics among high school students can serve as a catalyst for enhancing overall academic achievement. Educators and policymakers should prioritize efforts to strengthen mathematics education, as it not only contributes to students' mathematical skills but also has a ripple effect on their performance in other academic subjects.

Furthermore, the benefits of mathematics extend far beyond the confines of the classroom. It fosters resilience, perseverance, and problem-solving resilience, encouraging individuals to approach challenges with a growth mindset. Mathematical literacy enhances decision-making abilities, enabling individuals to make informed choices in their personal and professional lives.

This assessment seeks to investigate and comprehend the present state of mathematics performance among Junior High School Students at Labasan National High School. By examining the particular needs, strengths, and shortcomings in this domain, our objective is to formulate specific interventions tailored to address the challenges students encounter in mathematics. The ultimate aim is to promote sustainable development and achieve a more comprehensive and profound grasp of intricate mathematical concepts.

Mathematics stands as a cornerstone subject in both primary and secondary education, crucial for nurturing students' critical thinking, logical reasoning, problem-solving abilities, arithmetic skills, and higher-level cognitive processes. According to Abalde, G. D., et al. (2023), Students exhibit a notably positive attitude towards their study habits in mathematics learning, recognizing its significance. Their academic success and overall growth hinge largely on their performance in mathematics, emphasizing the

importance of mastering and understanding its concepts. The attitudes students hold towards their study habits significantly influence their approach to learning mathematics. Landicho, RR. (2021) states that student performance is influenced by factors such as study habits and interest, falling under student-related aspects, while teacher-related factors include instructional materials employed by educators. However, Villalobos, RN. (2020) highlighted that teacher-related issues, particularly instructional methodologies leading to passive learner participation, were the primary factors affecting the teaching-learning process. Additionally, inadequate teaching and learning materials were identified as contributors to students' performance issues in mathematics learning. Additionally, Wang, X. S., et al. (2023) suggest that the policy makers can tackle various factors, such as diminishing socioeconomic segregation among schools and the uneven distribution of educational resources, addressing shortages of teachers and support staff, enhancing teacher qualifications, and fostering the adoption of innovative teaching methods. Lastly, according to Tobias, C. A., et al. 2022) teachers must ensure that students have firmly grasped fundamental mathematical concepts to facilitate a smooth transition from basic to advanced lessons. This can be achieved through drills and interactive, student-centered teaching methods.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aims to determine the level of performance in Mathematics of Junior High School Students in Labasan National High School.

Specifically, this study aims to attain the following objectives:

1. Determine the level of performance of the Grade 7 students in Number and Number sense.
2. Determine the level of performance of the Grade 8 students in Patterns and Algebra.
3. Determine the level of performance of the Grade 9 students in Patterns and Algebra.
4. Determine the level of performance of the Grade 10 students in Patterns and Algebra.
5. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed descriptive research methodology to assess the performance levels in Mathematics among Junior High School Students at Labasan National High School. Descriptive research, as explained by Kelkar, G. (2023), it utilizes both quantitative and qualitative research methods to gather data for describing a phenomenon, situation, or population. In this research, descriptive methodology was utilized to characterize the performance levels of Grade 7 students in Number and

Number Sense, as well as Grade 8, 9, and 10 students in Patterns and Algebra through diagnostic exams.

The study was conducted at Labasan National High School, located in Barangay Labasan, Oriental Mindoro, with a student population of 470 encompassing both Junior and Senior High School levels. Respondents included Grade 7, Grade 8, Grade 9, and Grade 10 students, totaling 238 participants in Junior High School. Total enumeration sampling, as defined by Cononizado, I.C. (2021), was employed, which involves examining the entire population possessing specific characteristics.

A self-made test questionnaire aligned to the curriculum was utilized as the primary data collection tool to assess the mathematics performance levels of Junior High School students at Labasan National High School. The questionnaire comprised 30 multiple items covering the topics from the previous quarter. The questions are grouped according to the level of difficulty. Questionnaire was administered to 66 Grade 7 students, 50 Grade 8 students, 68 Grade 9 students, and 54 Grade 10 students.

Following the administration of the test questionnaire, collected data underwent sorting, tabulation, and interpretation using descriptive statistics, including frequency count and percentage analysis. Frequency count determined the occurrence of specific scores, while percentage analysis established the relationship between respondents' scores and the entire population. These statistical analyses were instrumental in evaluating the performance levels of Junior High School students in mathematics.

RESULTS

This presents the tabulation and textual representation of data used in the analysis and interpretation of the research objectives of the study.

1. Level of Performance of the Grade 7 students in Number and Number sense through Diagnostic Exam.

Table 1. Level of Performance of the Grade 7 students in Number and Number Sense

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Description
25-30	0	0	Very High
19-24	1	2	High
13-18	16	24	Average
7-12	45	68	Low
0-6	4	6	Very Low
	66	100	

Mean: 10.68	Low
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The table shows the level of Performance of Grade 7 students in number and number sense.

The table illustrates that only one or two percent of students achieved the highest scores within the range of 19-24, indicating a level considered as high. Conversely, four students, comprising six percent of the students, scored within the 0-6 range, categorized as very low. The overall mean score of 10.68 reflects a generally low performance in mathematics among the students.

2. Level of Performance of the Grade 8 students in Patterns and Algebra through Diagnostic Exam.

Table 2. Level of Performance of the Grade 8 students in Patterns and Algebra

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Description
25-30	0	0	Very High
19-24	2	4	High
13-18	18	36	Average
7-12	29	58	Low
0-6	1	2	Very Low
	50	100	
	Mean: 12.26		Low

The table shows the level of Performance of Grade 8 students in patterns and algebra.

Based on the table, it is noted that two students, equivalent to 4% of the total, attained the highest score range of 19-24, indicating a high performance in mathematics. Conversely, only one or 2% of students scored within the lowest range of 0-6, signaling very low performance. Despite this, the overall mean score of 12.26 suggests a generally low proficiency in mathematics among the students.

3. Level of Performance of the Grade 9 students in Patterns and Algebra through Diagnostic Exam.

Table 3. Level of Performance of the Grade 9 students in Patterns and Algebra

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Description
25-30	0	0	Very High
19-24	0	0	High
13-18	7	10	Average
7-12	55	81	Low
0-6	6	9	Very Low
	68	100	
	Mean: 9.31		Low

The table shows the level of Performance of Grade 9 students in patterns and algebra.

The tables revealed that seven students, constituting 10% of the students, achieved an average performance in mathematics. Conversely, six students, or 9% of the total, scored within the lowest range of 0-6, reflecting a very low performance level. With an overall mean score of 9.31, it is evident that a significant portion of the students exhibit low performance in mathematics.

4. Level of Performance of the Grade 10 students in Patterns and Algebra through Diagnostic Exam.

Table 4. Level of Performance of the Grade 10 students in Patterns and Algebra

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Description
25-30	0	0	Very High
19-24	2	4	High
13-18	14	26	Average
7-12	34	63	Low
0-6	4	7	Very Low
	54	100	
	Mean: 10.98		Low

The table shows the level of Performance of Grade 10 students in patterns and algebra.

The table indicates that merely two students, comprising 4% of the total, attained the highest score range of 19-24, indicative of high performance. However, four students, representing 7% of the students, exhibited a very low level of proficiency in mathematics. With an overall mean score of 10.98, it is evident that the students generally struggled with achieving low proficiency in mathematics.

5. Proposed Extension Program

Following the study's findings, by aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 4 (Quality Education), and SDG 5 (Gender Equality), the initiative demonstrates a commitment to broader global agendas while catering specifically to the needs of the Junior High School students in Labasan National High School, the researchers have introduced an extension program named MathPULSE: Powering Understanding through Learning Support and Education,. Developed through the collaborative efforts and expertise of the College of Teacher Education and the Mathematics Club at Mindoro State University – Bongabong Campus, this initiative aims to elevate students' proficiency in mathematics.

DISCUSSION

1. Level of Performance of the Grade 7 students in Number and Number sense through Diagnostic Exam.

Table 1 indicate that a significant portion of students are facing obstacles in their ability to understand and work with numbers effectively. It suggests that there are prevalent difficulties among students when it comes to grasping fundamental concepts of numerical comprehension and developing a strong sense of numbers. These challenges may manifest in various ways, such as struggles with basic arithmetic operations, difficulty interpreting numerical data, or an inability to apply mathematical concepts in real-world contexts. It underscores the importance of addressing these difficulties to ensure that all students have the necessary skills and knowledge to succeed in their mathematical learning journey.

According to Baker, MJ. (2019) recognizing the significance of number sense, educators must understand the strategies necessary to help all students develop this skill. One commonly employed instructional approach for teaching number sense is explicit instruction.

2. Level of Performance of the Grade 8 students in Patterns and Algebra through Diagnostic Exam.

Table 2 implies that, within the Grade 8 student, a significant proportion of the class may encounter challenges in understanding fundamental concepts, including pattern recognition, rule generalization, and algebraic reasoning. Students encountering difficulties with certain problems may choose not to attempt to answer the questions. These challenges likely contribute to the overall lower performance levels observed in mathematics. It underscores the importance of acknowledging diverse learning needs within the class and tailoring educational approaches to address these specific challenges in order to foster improved comprehension and academic achievement.

Bongala, J., et al. (2019) revealed that students who struggle to articulate their thoughts symbolically may experience a sense of inadequacy for not meeting expectations, leading them to refrain from attempting certain problems and consequently impacting their performance negatively.

3. Level of Performance of the Grade 9 students in Patterns and Algebra through Diagnostic Exam.

Table 3 emphasizes that there is a widespread deficiency in mastery among the student body, indicating that many students have not fully comprehended essential mathematical concepts and skills in patterns and algebra. This underscores the importance of acknowledging the issue and dedicating significant attention to addressing it. Without a solid grasp of foundational mathematical principles, students may encounter difficulties in advancing to more complex topics and may struggle to achieve academic.

It was supported by the findings of Compayan, LU., et.al (2019) concluded that a deficiency in mastering fundamental algebraic concepts, particularly in executing operations on algebraic expressions. As these concepts serve as foundational elements in algebra, the lack of comprehension and proficiency in any of these areas may impede the learners' advancement in higher mathematics education as they transition to subsequent academic levels.

4. Level of Performance of the Grade 10 students in Patterns and Algebra through Diagnostic Exam.

Table 4 implies that the students' struggles with low performance in mathematics could be attributed to difficulties in several key areas, including accurately executing algebraic operations, effectively solving equations, and proficiently manipulating mathematical expressions. These challenges may encompass various factors, such as a lack of

foundational understanding of mathematical concepts, insufficient practice with problem-solving techniques, or limited exposure to diverse mathematical scenarios.

According to Ying, C.L. et al. (2020), students struggle to achieve high scores in mathematics examinations due to their insufficient algebraic skills, which are essential for comprehending other mathematics subtopics. Proficiency in algebraic problem-solving is necessary for students to effectively learn and solve algebraic questions, enabling them to construct appropriate algebraic equations and arrive at accurate solutions.

5. Proposed Extension Program

MathPULSE: Powering Understanding through Learning Support and Education program provide essential instructional support and peer tutoring to comprehensively equip students for summative and final examinations. The significance of MathPULSE to students is underscored by its direct impact on their academic journey, particularly as they progress to higher grade levels and encounter the intricacies of mathematics courses. By leveraging the expertise and assistance available through the Mathematics Club and its skilled members, MathPULSE aims to address gaps in understanding and reinforce foundational concepts crucial for exam success. Furthermore, MathPULSE aligns with the broader objectives of the Mathematics Club's mission, engaging in supportive educational endeavors to foster mathematical competence and academic growth within the community. Through tailored educational support, the program not only facilitates immediate academic success but also cultivates enduring enthusiasm for mathematics, nurturing sustained growth and confidence in students' mathematical proficiency. Ultimately, MathPULSE serves as a testament to the Mathematics Club's commitment to academic excellence and community engagement. Through its provision of instructional support and peer tutoring, the program aims to strengthen students' academic foundation, ensuring their readiness for summative and final examinations while nurturing a lasting passion for mathematics within the academic environment. One of the aims of the MathPULSE program is to assist students in enhancing their understanding of challenging mathematical concepts. The program endeavors to achieve this by facilitating a clearer and more profound comprehension of complex mathematical concepts, thereby leading to enhanced performance in assessments, assignments, and examinations.

Conclusions

The findings highlight consistent challenges faced by Junior High School students at Labasan National High School in terms of mathematics performance. These scores reveal significant disparities, with only a small percentage of students achieving high scores, while a large proportion struggle to attain even average performance. The analysis indicates that the majority of students, regardless of grade level, encountered

difficulties in grasping fundamental mathematical concepts such as number sense, patterns, and algebra. This is evident from the consistently low mean scores observed across grade levels, indicating a widespread issue with mathematical performance among students.

Recommendations

To address these challenges, targeted interventions are recommended to address specific areas of weakness identified in students' mathematical performance. This could involve additional educational support sessions aimed at reinforcing foundational concepts. Additionally, enhancing training for mathematics teachers is recommended to provide professional development opportunities and improve instructional strategies and pedagogical approaches. Equipping teachers with the necessary tools and techniques will enable them to effectively address diverse learning needs and promote better mathematical understanding among students. Incorporating real-world applications and problem-solving tasks into the mathematics curriculum is also recommended to enhance student engagement and relevance. By contextualizing mathematical concepts within practical scenarios, students are more likely to develop a deeper understanding and appreciation for the subject. Encouraging a growth mindset among students is recommended by promoting resilience and a positive attitude towards learning mathematics. Emphasizing the importance of effort, practice, and learning from mistakes is crucial in achieving mathematical success. Furthermore, leveraging educational technology resources to supplement traditional classroom instruction is advised. This includes providing additional opportunities for practice and reinforcement, thereby enhancing student learning experiences. It is recommended for future researchers to undertake further studies aimed at identifying the factors influencing students' mathematical performance. This endeavor would facilitate the development of concrete programs or training initiatives tailored to both students and teachers. Implementing these recommendations can facilitate improvements in the overall mathematical performance of students and foster a positive learning environment conducive to academic success.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before commencing the research study, the researchers obtained permission from the School Head of Labasan National High School. They briefed the participants on the study's purpose and procedures. The researchers carefully observed and safeguarded participants' privacy and confidentiality while gathering data through respondents' answers to the test questionnaire. Ensuring that the study inflicted no harm upon the respondents, they aimed for its implementation to be beneficial.

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REFERENCES

- Abalde, G. D., & Oco, R. M. (2023). Factors Associated with Mathematics Performance. *Asian Research Journal of Mathematics*, 19(6), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.9734/arjom/2023/v19i6665>
- Baker, MJ. (2019). Number Sense and the Effects on Students' Mathematical Success. https://nwcommons.nwciowa.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1160&context=education_masters
- Bongala, J., et al. (2019). Factors Affecting Students' Performance in Generalizing Algebraic Patterns. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345002693_Factors_Affecting_Students'_Performance_in_Generalizing_Algebraic_Patterns
- Cabuquin, JC., et al. (2023). Mathematics Learners' Performance and Academic Achievement at a Public High School Institution in Leyte, Philippines. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30998/formatif.v13i2.17235>
- Chand, S., et al. (2021). Perceived Causes of Students' Poor Performance in Mathematics: A Case Study at Ba and Tavua Secondary Schools. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fams.2021.614408>
- Compayan, LU. et.al (2019). Level of achievement in algebra of grade seven learners. <https://journal.evsu.edu.ph/index.php/ajge>
- Cononizado, I.C. (2021). When to Use Total Population Sampling in a Research Study. <https://discover.hubpages.com/education/When-to-use-total-population-sampling-in-a-research-study>
- Kelkar, G. (2023). What is Descriptive Design and Why is It Important: The Ultimate Guide. <https://emeritus.org/blog/product-design-and-innovation-what-is-descriptive-design/>
- Landicho, RR. (2021). Factors Affecting Performance in General Mathematics of Grade Eleven Students in Talumpok Integrated School: Basis for Intervention Activities. <https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT21JAN248.pdf>
- OECD, PISA (2023). PISA 2022 results. <https://www.oecd.org/publication/pisa-2022-results/country-notes/philippines-a0882a2d/>
- Tobias, C. A., & Diego, C. V. (2022). Factors Predicting the Mathematics Performance of Grade 8 Students in the New Normal. *Asian Research Journal of Mathematics*, 18(11), 287–300.

- Villalobos, RN. (2020). Issues Affecting The Academic Performance In Mathematics Of Senior High School Students At Selected Schools In Zambales. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3652954
- Wang, X. S., Perry, L. B., Malpique, A., & Ide, T. (2023). Factors predicting mathematics achievement in PISA: A systematic review. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education*, 11(1), 1-42.
- Ying, C.L., et al (2020). Difficulties that Students Face when Learning Algebraic Problem-Solving. DOI: 10.13189/ujer.2020.081143